

Linear Free Energy Relationships in S_N2 Reactions

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The rates of reaction of a number of nucleophiles with 2, 4-dinitrochlorobenzene and picryl chloride have been measured in methyl alcohol. Relative nucleophilic reactivity parameters, ρ_{DNCB} and ρ_{PC} , have been computed. The applicability of Bronsted catalysis law and Edwards equation has been discussed. Attempt has been made to correlate the rate constants with amino proton chemical shift.

A number of attempts¹⁻⁵ have been made to correlate rate coefficients with other kinetic and thermodynamic data. These are all based on the principle of linear free-energy relationships⁶. Some of these include the Swain-Scott equation⁷, Bronsted relationships⁸, Hammett equation^{9,10}, and the Edwards equations^{11,12}. The latter are particularly interesting in that the oxidation potential of the nucleophile is considered as one of the parameters.

In the present communication, we have studied the rates of S_N2 reaction of a large number of nucleophiles with 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene and picryl chloride in methanol. An attempt has been made to use some of the linear free energy relationships and hence to compute the nucleophilic reactivity constants.

Experimental

Amines of the highest purity available were purified by recrystallising their salts. The amines were then distilled twice through sodium hydroxide pellets. Baker analysed methanol was used without further purification. Imidazole was crystallised from benzene. Picryl chloride (B.D.H.) and 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene were crystallised from alcohol-light petroleum and light petroleum several times before use.

Kinetic Measurement

50 ml of a solution of 0.04(M) halogeno compound and 0.08(M) with respect to amine were thermostated at the required temperatures. Aliquots were withdrawn at intervals and the reactions were analysed for chloride by Volhard's method, after partition

between 15 ml benzene, 10 ml water and 5 ml of silver nitrate solution. The aqueous layer together with 2×10 ml washings were titrated with standard ammonium thiocyanate solution

The rates of many of the reactions were also measured by following the changes in electrical conductivity using a Metrohm conductoscope E₃₆₅ and conductance cell EA 645.

Second order rate constants were calculated by leastsquares using Tobey's method¹³. The standard deviation of the individual plot was usually within 1% and agreement between duplicate was within 1-2%.

Discussion

Swain-Scott Equation :

The data obtained in the present investigation were converted into nucleophilic reactivity constants ρ_{DNCB} and ρ_{PC} (DNCB—2, 4-dinitrochlorobenzene, PC—Picryl chloride), which are defined as logarithms of the ratios of the second-order rate constants of the nucleophile divided by the second order rate constants for solvolysis in the solvent^{14,15}. Thus for a nucleophile Y,

$$\rho_{\text{DNCB}} = \log (k_Y/k_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}})$$
$$\text{and } \rho_{\text{PC}} = \log (k_Y/k_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}})$$

The k_Y corresponds to the rate constant of the nucleophile.

Swain-Scott⁷, and Pearson and coworkers^{14,15} used the same convention for computing the nucleophilicity parameter values for CH_3I and some platinum

complexes. The n_{PC} values have been computed at 30° and the $n_{DN CB}$ values have been computed at 40°C. We will assume that the change with temperature is small in this range. The same assumption has also been adopted by Pearson¹⁵ for computing n_{Pt} and n_{CH_3I} values. The values of $n_{DN CB}$ and n_{PC} are summarised in Table 1. A scrutiny of $n_{DN CB}$ and n_{PC} values indicates that they are approximately equal for all the nucleophiles except for α -naphthylamine and triphenyl phosphine. It is, therefore, postulated that as long as the mechanism is the same, an alteration in the environment or temperature does not substantially affect the nucleophilic reactivity constants¹⁵.

A plot of $\log k(\text{DN CB-bases})$ vs $n_{DN CB}$ and $\log k(\text{PC-bases})$ vs n_{PC} yielded excellent linear plots. This suggests a linear free energy relationship

$$\log k_Y = sn + \log k_s$$

The values of s , the nucleophilic discrimination factor were computed to be 1 and 1.1 for DN CB and PC respectively. Pearson and coworkers¹⁴ have computed the s values ranging from 0.44 to 1.43 for different platinum complexes using the same nucleophiles. A large value of s means that the substrate (activated aromatic halide) is very sensitive to changes in the nature of the nucleophilic reagent¹⁴.

Bronsted Relationships

Although bimolecular nucleophilic substitutions have received intensive attention¹⁶, relatively few data are available for any systematic investigation of correlation between the S_N2 nucleophilic reactivity and base dissociation constants. The use of the extended Bronsted relationship¹⁷ has become almost common place as a mechanistic probe. It has been used in connection with nucleophilic substitution at aliphatic^{17,18}, aromatic and carbonyl carbon¹⁹, at

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AND NUCLEOPHILICITY REACTIVITY CONSTANTS FOR VARIOUS NUCLEOPHILES.

S.No.	Nucleophile	$K_{DN CB} \times 10^4$ (40°C)	$n_{DN CB}$	$K_{PC} \times 10^3$ (30°C)	n_{PC}	pK _a	En
		$1.\text{mole}^{-1}\text{sec}^{-1}$		$1.\text{mole}^{-1}\text{sec}^{-1}$			
1.	Aniline	14.13	3.26	17.80	3.45	4.59	1.78 ^a
2.	Benzylamine	21.10	3.44	60.80	3.98	—	1.77 ^b
3.	Diethylamine	98.00	4.10	119.00	4.27	11.0	1.94 ^b
4.	Dimethylaniline	—	—	10	3.20	5.06	—
5.	α -naphthylamine	4.60	2.78	21.50	3.53	—	1.30 ^b
6.	α -Picoline	4.00	3.80	17.40	3.44	6.48	—
7.	Piperidine	56.00	3.86	67.00	4.00	11.21	—
8.	Pyridine	—	—	12.00	3.28	—	1.20 ^a
9.	Quinoline	1.68	2.34	—	—	—	—
10.	<i>p</i> -Chloro Aniline	5.37	2.84	3.89	2.79	3.98	1.22 ^b
11.	<i>p</i> -toluidine	24.55	3.50	56.30	3.95	5.01	1.44 ^b
12.	<i>m</i> -toluidine	19.45	3.41	34.51	3.74	4.73	1.35 ^b
13.	<i>o</i> -toluidine	16.60	3.33	14.12	3.34	4.45	1.27 ^b
14.	Triphenyl phosphine	39.81	1.71	5.50	2.9	2.73	—
15.	Imidazole	10	3.13	13.33	3.32	7.10	—

^a R. G. PEARSON, H. SOBEL and J. SONGSTAD., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 318.

^b P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTY and G. P. PANIGRAHI, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 318.

phosphorus²⁰ and at sulphur²¹. The magnitude of the Bronsted coefficient has usually been related to the extent of bond formation in the transition state and when an intermediate is formed along the reaction path, a large Bronsted coefficient is expected²².

The data for the reaction of substituted anilines with 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene and picryl chloride were fitted against the pK_a values of the corresponding amines. The values of β, the Bronsted coefficient were calculated to be 0.85 for DNCB and 1.25 for PC respectively. Similar data for reactions of phenoxides with picryl chloride²³ is correlated with a lower Bronsted slope. In fact, the Bronsted coefficient for oxygen nucleophiles (β=0.80) was measured almost in the same medium and with the same substrate as those reported in this paper for nitrogen nucleophiles. The Bronsted slopes are, therefore, characteristic of the nucleophiles. According to the significance generally attached to the Bronsted 'β' values, it seems that more bond formation between the nucleophiles and the reaction centre at the rate-limiting transition state is involved for reactions with neutral nucleophiles than for reactions with anionic nucleophiles²⁴. This is in agreement with predictions²⁵ from the Ogg-Polanyi-Hammond principle²⁶. A slope of 0.24 was found for the reaction of phenoxides with *p*-nitrophenyl triphenylmethane sulphonate²⁷ and 1.5 for the reaction of anilines with the same substrate in dioxanewater mixtures. The obvious conclusion seems to be that, with oxygen nucleophiles, there is very little bond formation in the transition state while with nitrogen nucleophiles an S_AN mechanism is operative²⁸.

The value of Bronsted coefficient was computed to be 0.35 for other types of nucleophiles with DNCB. At the present situation it is very difficult to say anything definite regarding this low value for other nucleophiles. But it may be suggested that factors such as solvent, steric compression at the reaction centre, nature of the nucleophilic atom, and leaving group could bring about different transition states for which different Bronsted coefficient may be conceived.

A scattered plot is observed when the n_{DNCB} and n_{PC} values are plotted against the pK_a values of the nucleophiles. The same observation has been noted by Pearson¹⁵ et al. while correlating the n_{pt} values against the pK_a values of the nucleophiles. It may be concluded that most probably there may not be any correlation between the nucleophilicity parameters and the strength of the nucleophiles.

Edwards Equation—

The Edwards equation¹¹

$$\log k/k_0 = \alpha_{E_N} + \beta_H$$

has been quite successful in correlating a very wide range of data, including both kinetic and thermodynamic results from organic and inorganic systems. Davies²⁹, in particular, has shown that the above equation is quantitatively good for both nucleophilic displacements on tetrahedral carbon and divalent sulphur. Since,

$$H = pK_a + 1.74$$

it is suggested that the equation be called the oxibase scale³⁰.

In the absence of large number of E_n values, we have only included a very small number of nucleophiles in the present investigation. The E_n values used are those computed by Pearson¹⁵ and Radhakrishnamurthy³¹. The logarithm of the rate data have been plotted against the electrode potential values. All the plots were perfectly linear, indicating the general applicability of the E_n values in reactions of the same mechanistic pathway.

Linear plots were also obtained when the n_{DNCB} and n_{PC} values were plotted against the E_n values. Such correlation has also been made by Pearson before¹⁵.

A plot of n_{DNCB} against n_{PC} is linear with a slope of 1.1. A similar slope (1.4) has been obtained by Pearson¹⁵ and coworkers while plotting n_{CH₃I} against n_{pt}.

Relationship between rate constants and chemical shifts

In recent years, the amino-proton chemical shifts of 12 meta- and para- substituted anilines have been measured in carbontetrachloride by Dyall³² and 41 ortho-, meta- and para- substituted anilines in cyclohexanone by Yonemoto and his coworkers³³. Akiyama and coworkers³⁴ have correlated the chemical shift values of the substituted anilines with Hammett constants and excellent plot has been observed except for ortho- substituted compounds.

In the present investigation, the rate data have been correlated with amino-proton chemical shift for

meta- and para- substituted anilines both for picryl chloride and 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene. Excellent plots were obtained in each case. This indicates that the reactivity of the amino-group is governed only by the electron density on the nitrogen atom.

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